

SEVEN SECRETS OF DEVELOPING THE NATURAL AND SCIENTIFIC OUTLOOK OF 5-8 CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *In this article, the seven secrets of more effective learning of natural geographical knowledge are covered in detail, and the methods of making students interested in science and helping students learn geographical knowledge more easily in classes are discussed.*

Keywords: *the first 20 minutes, victory in the classroom, connecting theory to practice, miller's purse, memory exercise.*

In order to be successful and competitive, a person should always work on himself and educate himself. What is the secret to ensure effective learning in this process?

1 - the secret - to use the first 20 minutes optimally when learning a very difficult material, not to overexert the brain and change the type of exercises in the next minutes. Therefore, it is important to change the type of work in mastering a complex subject. For example, we feel tired when solving problems related to changes in air temperature and air pressure as we go up, or when we study the definition of natural geographical processes. This is our body's defense mechanism, which protects us from excessive stress.

A person can concentrate at a high level only during the first 20 minutes. After half an hour, as a result of the division of attention, the reception of information slows down to 60% and after 45 minutes to 40%. Therefore, knowledge with a high level of complexity becomes more and more difficult to understand after an hour.

2- secret - victory in class. Make it a habit to evaluate your achievements in class and after class. Such an approach will help you to eliminate negative aspects of the learning process, increase educational motivation and independence. Identify your shortcomings and try to eliminate them. Do this exercise regularly. Then you start to control yourself and make fewer mistakes. Always learn to ask questions in class and after class to help you learn more effectively. For example: Do this exercise regularly. Then you start to control yourself and make fewer mistakes. Always learn to ask questions in class and after class to help you learn more effectively. For example:

- What is the most important thing I learned today?

Write your answer directly in your workbook.

- What questions are unclear to me?

Write these questions down immediately, and if possible, ask and answer the teacher.

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3 - secret - connecting theory with practice. Theoretical knowledge is strengthened and improved by practice. Sometimes we do not understand what some words are about, even if we are familiar with them. We cannot determine the meaning of the word. Are you familiar with this

problem? What does our brain do with the information we don't use? That's right, it puts it in a "long archive" so as not to waste energy. For example, climate-forming factors are important in the formation of local climate, or in the relief of the Central Asian country, there are mainly mountains, highlands, depressions between mountains and high plains. considering it as secondary, abstract information, our brain places it in the "long archive". But if we say that the highest place in Central Asia is Chogori Peak (8611 m) in the Karakorum Range, and the lowest place is Torfon Botig (-154 m) in the Taklamakan Desert, then the brain also focuses on it and considers it as important information. In the 5th grade, it is mentioned that "air temperature is measured using a thermometer." But if we bring a thermometer in the lesson, give it to the student's hand and understand that it is necessary to measure it at a height of 2 meters in the shade, we will make the student interested in our science, this lesson will remain in the student's memory for years. But if we say that the highest place in Central Asia is Chogori Peak (8611 m) in the Karakorum Range, and the lowest place is Torfon Botig (-154 m) in the Taklamakan Desert, then the brain also focuses on it and considers it as important information. In the 5th grade, it is mentioned that "air temperature is measured using a thermometer." But if we bring a thermometer in the lesson, give it to the student's hand and understand that it is necessary to measure it at a height of 2 meters in the shade, we will make the student interested in our science, this lesson will remain in the student's memory for years. The third secret of successful learning is to gain knowledge and skills through direct experience. This is exactly what it means to be "shy and shy", which means that the most important thing is to consciously apply the theoretical knowledge we have learned. Here I will talk about the term mne-monica, which is often used in recent times. Mnemonics means the art of remembering. For example, it is easier to remember high mountain peaks if they are studied in groups depending on their height or belonging to the continent.

4 - secret - imagination. It is no secret that imagination gives great opportunities to perceive information. However, it has a big drawback - it cannot save the received data for a long time. The brain's attention filters filter out unnecessary information to save brain energy. American psychologist George Miller developed a theory called "Miller's wallet" and later it became known as "Rule of 7 ± 2 ". The summary of the rule is that a person's short-term memory cannot remember more than 9 objects. Miller's wallet. The short-term memory or special "wallet" in the human brain can hold no more than "seven coins" of different values at the same time. If there are more than seven or more than nine, the brain intuitively divides them into groups of 5 to 9. There is a direct connection between the efficiency of our work and the number 7. For example, imagine your desk. Miller's wallet. The short-term memory or special "wallet" in the human brain can hold no more than "seven coins" of different values at the same time. If there are more than seven or more than nine, the brain intuitively divides them into groups of 5 to 9. There is a direct connection between the efficiency of our work and the number 7. For example, imagine your desk. If the number of things in it is more than seven, the brain perceives it as disorder. According to experiments, the productivity of a person's work increases after he organizes his desk. Compliance with the 7 ± 2 rule helps to save time, solve various problems, and especially manage processes more effectively. Miller's experiments showed that, on average, a person's short-term memory can remember nine two-digit numbers, eight multi-digit numbers, seven letters of the alphabet, and five one-syllable words.

5- secret - effective repetition. Based on the research of Hermann Ebbinghaus, the curve-based repetition technique. Following this simple technique allows you to easily store up to 4 times

as much material without straining your long-term memory. In order for the human brain to retain information for a sufficiently long time, it is necessary to refer to it several times in a certain period of time. But there should be rest periods between application periods. But there should be rest periods between repetitions. Information read the night before the exam is stored in our short-term memory, but information obtained in this way does not go to long-term memory. Brainstorming is useful for generating new ideas, but not for memorizing anything. As a result of a short-term, one-time movement of the brain, there is little opportunity to fully absorb information, or it cannot remember for a long time what it has absorbed so quickly. When memorizing information, it is important to understand it and understand its meaning. German Ebbinghaus discovered algorithms that can significantly increase the capacity of memory. Many methods of learning and memorizing information were created based on his research. The scientist came to the conclusion that polyglots are not born, but formed. If you need to remember for a very long time:

- the first repetition after the initial reading; - the second repetition 20-30 minutes after the first repetition;

- the third repetition is 1 day after the second; - the fourth repetition 2-3 after the third;
- the fifth repetition should be done 2-3 months after the fourth repetition.

Thus, the effective repetition method allows you to retain four times more new information in memory than the traditional method.

"Knowledge is the fruit of repetition and repetition" Abu Raikhan Beruni

Memory exercise. We will be divided into 5 small groups. Each small group will make a list of 15 names, countries, rivers, lakes, deserts and mountains according to the given direction within 2 minutes. Each team in turn shows the list to the class for 40 seconds. After forty seconds, the list is closed, the groups must say the words shown in the list in order in thirty seconds. Xotira mashqi.

6- the secret - regular movements. It is regular movements that make your activities routine like soft water crushes hard rock. Consistent performance of assigned tasks will lead to effective results. Mastering a task through repetition confirms that the power is not only in knowledge, but in the actions towards the goal.

7- secret - proper systematization of learning. In your notebook, you must clearly reflect all the details of the above secrets, that is:

- clearly and clearly define the purpose of the training
- get detailed information about exercises and tasks
- formation of targeted knowledge and skills, when problematic issues are identified, strive to solve them immediately

- apply the acquired knowledge
- pay attention to the compatibility with the purpose of the actions.

Strive for knowledge! If you work diligently towards your goal, nothing can stand in your way. If we follow the right and effective way of acquiring knowledge, we will achieve our goals in a short time with great confidence.

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